

The Growth of Labour Productivity in the Global Innovation Index

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The variable "labour productivity growth" in the Global Innovation Index (GII) measures the efficiency with which a country's or region's workforce produces goods and services. It represents the percentage increase in value added per worker or per hour worked over a given period, indicating whether and to what extent people are becoming more productive. This variable is relevant in the context of the GII because it reflects a country's level of innovation and technological efficiency. Labour productivity growth can result from greater adoption of new technologies, improvements in organizational processes, workforce training and skill development, and improved production infrastructure. A high growth in labour productivity signals an economy that is evolving towards high-value-added sectors capable of generating innovative products or services. Conversely, stagnation or decline may indicate structural difficulties or inefficient use of human and technological resources. Improving labour productivity is thus a key goal for countries aspiring to strengthen their international competitiveness and stimulate sustainable economic growth. The data refer to the period between 2021 and 2022.

Labour Productivity Growth in 2022. The data on labour productivity growth for 2022 shows a wide range of variations across countries, highlighting differences in economic, technological, and infrastructural development globally. China leads the ranking with a labour productivity growth of 100%, followed by countries such as Tajikistan (94.3%), Vietnam (93%), and Romania (92.2%). These countries show significant progress in terms of productive efficiency, often due to investments in technology, infrastructure, and workforce training. China, in particular, has benefited from strong innovative and industrial momentum in recent decades, becoming a global economic powerhouse. Countries like Vietnam and Bangladesh (90.6%) have also seen productivity acceleration, partly due to the relocation of manufacturing industries from more developed countries. Many countries fall into the growth range between 60% and 75%. Countries such as India (75.2%), Colombia (76.7%), Egypt (75.7%), and Poland (70.8%) fall into this group, indicating significant productivity growth, but not as rapid as that of the top-performing countries. India, although one of the largest emerging economies, shows moderate growth, likely due to the need for further improvements in infrastructure and the distribution of technological innovations throughout the country. In Europe, Poland and the Baltic countries, such as Estonia (74.6%) and Lithuania (74.4%), show solid growth, supported by policies that encourage innovation and digitization. Singapore (70.9%), despite its advanced and strong economy, shows solid but not exceptional growth. This could be attributed to a saturated technological market or productivity stabilization after years of rapid growth.

Developed Economies with Lower Growth. Surprisingly, many of the major developed economies show relatively low productivity growth. The United States (59.1%), Israel (66.7%), and South Korea (59.8%) fall into a lower growth range compared to some developing countries. This may reflect a situation where innovation and technology are already integrated into the economies, but the margins for improvement are reduced. Moreover, factors such as demographics, market maturity, and already

high levels of productivity may make it harder to achieve further gains. Western Europe shows relatively low growth, with countries such as France (47.4%), Germany (46.6%), Italy (45.2%), and Spain (38.6%) displaying productivity values much lower than those of emerging countries. These countries, which have mature economies, may face structural challenges, such as rigid labor markets, aging populations, and slower adoption of new technologies. Finally, there are countries showing very low labour productivity growth, such as Saudi Arabia (14.5%), Iraq (9.9%), and Angola (7.7%). These countries often face significant economic and political challenges that hinder growth. For example, Iraq's economy has been severely affected by conflict and political instability, limiting its ability to grow in terms of productivity. Similarly, many Sub-Saharan African countries, such as Namibia (15.4%) and Angola, struggle to improve their economic efficiency due to poor infrastructure and a lack of investment in technology and human capital. Overall, the data show a correlation between labour productivity growth and the economic and technological development of countries. Emerging economies are generally experiencing faster productivity gains, while advanced economies are seeing more moderate growth. However, structural, political, and technological challenges continue to affect countries' ability to improve their workforce efficiency.

Labour Productivity Growth between 2021 and 2022. The data on labour productivity growth between 2021 and 2022 show significant global differences, with countries experiencing sharp increases as well as drastic declines. Labour productivity reflects how efficiently a country utilizes its workforce to produce goods and services. Variations in the data can be influenced by factors such as investments in technology, infrastructure, education, economic policies, and economic or geopolitical crises. Among the countries that have seen the largest increases in labour productivity, Iran stands out with an 80.5% increase (an absolute change of 23.5 points). This increase could be linked to internal reforms or improved economic conditions despite difficulties related to international sanctions. Other countries like Romania (+31.7%), Bahrain (+30.9%), and Singapore (+26.6%) have also seen significant growth. These countries have likely benefited from improved productive efficiency, investments in new technologies, and improvements in infrastructure and workforce training. In Europe, Moldova has seen notable growth (+37.7%), indicating significant economic progress. Romania has continued to improve its economic performance, likely due to continued integration with European markets and foreign investments. Malta and Mauritius, with increases of 28.0% and 22.6%, respectively, demonstrate how even small economies can achieve remarkable results by focusing on strategic sectors and modernizing their economic approach. Some countries, such as the United Kingdom (+22.3%), Croatia (+20.6%), and Zimbabwe (+20.5%), have seen moderate productivity growth. These increases indicate improvements but possibly also limits in the ability to further increase productivity, potentially due to structural or economic factors. China, with a 14.3% increase, continues to grow, but at a more moderate pace than in previous years, suggesting that the country may have reached a more stable phase in productivity growth, where marginal gains are harder to achieve. On the opposite side, many countries have experienced significant declines in labour productivity. Saudi Arabia saw the sharpest decline, with a 68.6% decrease, followed by Angola (-77.2%) and Namibia (-61%). These declines may be linked to economic crises, political instability, or natural disasters. For example, Saudi Arabia may have been affected by fluctuations in oil prices, which represent a substantial part of its economy. Other countries like Peru (-35.3%), Nigeria (-35.1%), and Rwanda (-32.4%) have seen significant decreases, likely due to economic difficulties related to the COVID-19 pandemic, political unrest, or internal economic crises. Latin American countries such as Brazil (-18.9%) and Argentina (-26.1%) continue to suffer from economic instability, inflation, and political crises, which severely impact the ability to improve workforce efficiency. Many developed countries have experienced declines in labour productivity. The United States saw a decrease of 11.8%, while Canada (-15.4%), Japan (-14.5%), and Germany (-5.5%) also

registered declines. This could indicate stagnation in advanced economies, where innovation is no longer able to offset rising costs or structural inefficiencies.

Conclusions. Labour productivity growth decreased on average between 2021 and 2022 by an amount equal to -6.5%, falling from 60.02 units to 56.12 units. The top performers were Iran (+80.5%), Moldova (+37.7%), Romania (+31.7%), Bahrain (+30.9%), and Malta (+28.0%). The worst performers were Oman (-43.2%), Kuwait (-48.5%), Namibia (-61.0%), Saudi Arabia (-68.6%), and Angola (-77.2%).

References

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at World Level. Available at SSRN 4420946.

Massaro, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Leogrande, A., & Cannone, F. (2022, February). Use of machine learning to predict the glyceemic status of patients with diabetes. In *Medical Sciences Forum* (Vol. 10, No. 1, p. 11). MDPI.

Leogrande, A. (2023). Ammonia Emissions in Europe. International Web Post.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Impact of Government Expenditure on Education in the ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4438106.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The fight against corruption at global level. A metric approach. *A Metric Approach* (December 30, 2022).

Leogrande, A. (2024). Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4772381.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4771131.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level. *Discover Global Society*, 2(1), 1.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Mortality from Nervous System Diseases in Italian Regions. International.

Appendix

Performance	Countries	2021	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Best Performers	Iran, Islamic Rep.	29,2	52,7	23,5	80,5
	Moldova	51,4	70,8	19,4	37,7
	Romania	70	92,2	22,2	31,7
	Bahrain	56,6	74,1	17,5	30,9
	Malta	36,1	46,2	10,1	28,0
Worse Performers	Oman	47,9	27,2	-20,7	-43,2
	Kuwait	51,3	26,4	-24,9	-48,5
	Namibia	39,5	15,4	-24,1	-61,0
	Saudi Arabia	46,2	14,5	-31,7	-68,6
	Angola	33,8	7,7	-26,1	-77,2

